

Web Appendix 2 - Setting Thresholds for Decision Making

The first step of our study was to perform a test run of papers on their social impact orientation—that is, in addressing the SDGs and the Seven Principles of Responsible Research. We applied ChatSDG+RR7 to the 141 papers that had previously been reviewed and accepted through the traditional peer review process for the RRBM Honor Roll, scoring them on the scale from 0-5. The ratings of all the papers are shown in Figure 3 below with the dotted line. What can be observed is that ChatSDG+RR7 did not always agree with the determination made by the previous peer review evaluation.

Figure 3

Previously accepted Honor Roll submissions with editor and reviewers only

Based on this training, thresholds were established for recommending acceptance labeled “pass” (scores above 4.5) and rejection labeled “cut” (scores below 4.1), with scores falling in between labeled as “human review.” There were 59 out of the 141 papers that clearly met the “pass” threshold, agreeing with the previous decision, and 64 that would be recommended for

“human review” (that is, agreement with less certainty). There was disagreement about these remaining 18 papers because, although previously accepted to the Honor Roll through human peer review, they were flagged for “cut” under the new evaluation process.

The next step was processing the 322 papers awaiting review by the Honor Roll editorial team (Web Appendix 3).